

Some New Parameterized Fractional Inequalities For Hermite-Hadamard Type With Application

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Abstract

Overall, the ongoing interest in the use of fractional operators in integral inequalities reflects their importance and potential for advancing mathematical theory and its applications across multiple disciplines. The paper introduces fractional Hermite-Hadamard type inequalities that are parameterized. These inequalities derived for functions whose third derivative in absolute values are quasi-convexity. By assigning specific values to the parameter in the fractional parameterized inequalities, the paper presents several new results for Hermite-Hadamard type inequalities. These results include both novel findings and previously known results, as indicated by Corollaries 1, and 2-7. Additionally, the paper explores an application of the derived inequalities to special means of real numbers.

1 Introduction

Convexity theory provides powerful tools for analyzing and solving problems across a wide range of disciplines. In addition to integral inequalities, convexity theory also provides insights into various other properties of functions, such as the behaviour of their derivatives, the curvature of their graphs, and the existence of unique solutions to certain mathematical and applied problems. Convex functions exhibit stability properties that make them robust against small perturbations. This stability is particularly useful in applications such as machine learning and signal processing, where noise or uncertainty is present.

The Hermite-Hadamard type (H-H) inequality [1] has important applications in various fields, including analysis, optimization, and economics. It is often used to derive inequalities, establish bounds, and prove theorems in these areas. Additionally, the inequality has extensions and generalizations to different settings, such as functions defined on convex sets. The Hermite-Hadamard type (H-H) inequality, named after Charles Hermite and Jacques Hadamard, has indeed been extensively studied and generalized over the years, making it an essential tool in mathematical analysis. Researchers have made significant contributions to its development and extension to various contexts, enriching its applicability and utility in different areas of mathematics and beyond. The exploration of various generalizations, extensions, and refinements of the Hermite-Hadamard type

(H-H) inequality, involving different types of functions, operators, and integral formulations. Here are some notable examples of such efforts. Bayraktar et al. [2] introduced Mercer versions of the Hermite-Hadamard type (H-H) inequality, which involve generalizations to functions satisfying certain conditions related to Mercer's theorem. Sahoo et al [3] established Hermite-Hadamard type (H-H) inequalities via Atangana-Baleanu fractional operators. Yang et al [4] presented midpoint-type inequalities using Caputo-Fabrizio fractional operators. Researchers, such as those cited in reference [5, 6], have explored new versions of the Hermite-Hadamard type (H-H) inequality involving exponential kernels. Bayraktar et al., as referenced in [7], employed modified (h, m, s) convex functions to establish weighted Hermite-Hadamard type (H-H) inequalities. Alomari et al [8] proved the refinements of Hermite-Hadamard type (H-H) inequalities for quasi-convex. Kirmaci et al [9] derived inequalities for a differentiable function and give application to midpoint formula.

In recent years the extension of the Hermite-Hadamard type (H-H) inequality to fractional calculus allows researchers to analyze the properties of fractional integral operators and their relationships with convex functions. This analysis can lead to the derivation of fractional integral inequalities, which provide bounds on integrals involving fractional operators and convex functions. The fractional Hermite-Hadamard type (H-H) inequality indeed explores the behaviour of fractional integrals of convex functions, serving as a bridge between the realms of

convexity theory and fractional calculus. By considering fractional operators of different orders, such as the Riemann-Liouville or Caputo fractional operators, this inequality establishes relationships between the fractional integral of a convex function and its endpoint values. In doing so, it reveals intriguing properties and insights into the behaviour of these functions in the context of fractional calculus. The exploration of fractional Hermite-Hadamard type (H-H) inequalities has led to advancements in inequality theory, particularly in the study of integral inequalities involving convex functions and fractional operators. Researchers have developed new techniques and methods for deriving and analyzing these inequalities, contributing to a deeper understanding of their properties and implications see these articles [10-13]. Nasira et al [14] derived Hermite-Hadamard type (H-H) inequalities for Caputao-Fabrizio operator. Mumcu et al [15] established Hermite-Hadamard type (H-H) inequalities using the generalized proportional fractional integral. By introducing new operator, establishing novel inequalities, deriving interesting identities, exploring special cases, and demonstrating practical applications, the paper contributes to the ongoing development and enrichment of mathematical theory and its applications. We recall some well knows operator and generalized convexity as fellows.

1.1 Preliminaries

Definition 1 [16] The mapping of $f : I \subseteq \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is said to be convex if:

$$f(ta + (1-t)b) \leq tf(a) + (1-t)f(b),$$

for all $a, b \in I$ and $t \in [0, 1]$

Definition 2 [17] A function $f : [a, b] \subset \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is said quasi-convex on $[a, b]$ if:

$$f(ta + (1-t)b) \leq \max[f(a), f(b)]$$

for all $a, b \in [a, b]$ and $t \in [0, 1]$.

Definition 3 [18] Let $H^1(a, b)$ be the Sobolev space of order one defined as

$$H^1(a, b) = \{g \in L^2(a, b) : g' \in L^2(a, b)\},$$

where

$$L^2(a, b) = \left\{ g(z) : \left(\int_a^b g^2(z) dz \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} < \infty \right\}.$$

let $f \in H^1(a, b)$, $a < b$, $\alpha \in [0, 1]$, then the notion of left derivative in the sense of Caputo-Fabrizio is defined as:

$$\left({}_a^{CFD} D^\alpha f \right)(x) = \frac{\beta(\alpha)}{1-\alpha} \int_a^x f'(t) e^{\frac{-\alpha(x-t)^\alpha}{1-\alpha}} dt,$$

$x > a$ and the associated integral operator is

$$\left({}_a^{CF} I^\alpha f \right)(x) = \frac{1-\alpha}{\beta(\alpha)} f(x) + \frac{\alpha}{\beta(\alpha)} \int_a^x f(t) dt$$

where $\beta(\alpha) > 0$ is the normalization function satisfying $\beta(0) = \beta(1) = 1$. For $\alpha = 0, \alpha = 1$, the left derivative is defined as follows, respectively

$$\left({}_a^{CFD} D^0 f \right)(x) = f'(x)$$

$$\left({}_a^{CFD} D^1 f \right)(x) = f(x) - f(a).$$

For the right derivative operator

$$\left({}_b^{CFD} D^\alpha f \right)(x) = \frac{\beta(\alpha)}{1-\alpha} \int_x^b f'(\psi) e^{\frac{-\alpha(t-x)^\alpha}{1-\alpha}} dt,$$

$x < b$ and the associated integral operator is

$$\left({}_b^{CF} I^\alpha f \right)(x) = \frac{1-\alpha}{\beta(\alpha)} f(x) + \frac{\alpha}{\beta(\alpha)} \int_x^b f(t) dt,$$

where $\beta(\alpha) > 0$ is a normalization function that satisfies $\beta(0) = \beta(1) = 1$.

Inequalities for three times differentiable mappings and applications to special means are given by Qaisar et. al [19].

Theorem 1 Let $f : I \subset \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a differentiable function on I° , $a, b \in I^\circ$ with $a < b$. If $f''' \in L[a, b]$ is convex on $[a, b]$, then the following inequality holds:

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{\beta(\alpha)}{\alpha(b-a)} \left[\left({}_a^{CF} I^\alpha f \right)(k) + \left({}_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{CF} I^\alpha f \right)(k) + \left({}_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{CF} I^\alpha f \right)(k) + \left({}_b^{CF} I^\alpha f \right)(k) \right] \right. \\ & \left. - f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) - \frac{(b-a)^2}{24} f''\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \right| \\ & \leq \frac{(b-a)^3}{384} \left(|f'''(a)| + |f'''(b)| \right). \end{aligned}$$

In [20] Ling Chun is established the Hermite-Hadamard type inequality as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + \frac{b-a}{24} \left(|f'(b)| - |f'(a)| \right) - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) dx \right| \\ & \leq \frac{(b-a)^3}{384} \left[\left(\frac{4|f'(a)|^q + 11|f'(b)|^q}{15} \right) + \left(\frac{11|f'(a)|^q + 4|f'(b)|^q}{15} \right) \right]^{\frac{1}{q}}, \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\left| \frac{f(a) + f(b)}{2} - \frac{b-a}{12} (f'(b) - f'(a)) - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) dx \right|$$

$$\leq \frac{(b-a)^3}{192} \left(\frac{2^{2-s}(2^{2+s}s+s+6)}{(s+2)(s+3)(s+4)} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \left[|f'''(a)|^q, |f'''(b)|^q \right]^{\frac{1}{q}}.$$

The objective of this research paper is to advance the field of convexity theory and the Hermite-Hadamard (H-H) inequality. We will focus on introducing the new parameterizing identity. Based on this identity these parameterizing inequalities and assigning specific values to the parameter, we derive several new results for Hermite-Hadamard (H-H) inequalities. These findings encompass both original contributions and previously known results, as demonstrated by Corollaries 1, and 2-7. Furthermore, we explore the practical application of these derived inequalities to special means of real numbers. Through these efforts, our paper aims to deepen our understanding of convexity theory, fractional calculus, and their interconnectedness, while also offering valuable insights for practical problem-solving in various domains.

2 An Critical Identity

To establish the results of this section regarding Caputo-Fabrizio fractional integral operators, we start by proving the following lemma:

Lemma 1 Let $f : I^o \subset \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and $\varepsilon \in \mathbb{R}$ be a three

differentiable function on I^o , $a, b \in I^o$ with $a < b$. If $f''' \in L[a, b]$ and $\alpha \in [0, 1]$, then the following fractional parameterized equality holds:

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(\frac{(4-\varepsilon)f(a) + (\varepsilon+2)f(mb)}{2} \right) - \frac{\beta(\alpha)}{\alpha(mb-a)} \left[({}^{CF}I_a^\alpha f)(k) + ({}^{CF}I_{mb}^\alpha f)(k) \right] \\ & - \frac{b-a}{12} (\varepsilon f'(mb) - (2-\varepsilon)f'(a)) + \frac{2(1-\alpha)}{\beta(\alpha)} f(k) \\ & = \frac{(mb-a)^3}{12} \int_0^1 t(1-t)(2t-\varepsilon) f'''(ta + (1-t)b) dt. \end{aligned}$$

where $\beta(\alpha) > 0$ is the normalization function.

Proof. By integration by parts, we get

$$\begin{aligned} I &= \frac{(mb-a)^3}{12} \int_0^1 t(1-t)(2t-\varepsilon) f'''(ta + m(1-t)b) dt \\ &= \frac{1}{mb-a} \int_0^1 (2(2+\varepsilon)t - \varepsilon - 6t^2) f''(ta + m(1-t)b) dt \\ &= \frac{1}{(mb-a)^2} (\varepsilon + 6t^2 - 2(2+\varepsilon)t) f'(ta + m(1-t)b) \Big|_0^1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & - \frac{1}{(mb-a)^2} \int_0^1 (\varepsilon + 6t^2 - 2(2+\varepsilon)t) f'(ta + m(1-t)b) dt \\ &= \frac{-1}{(mb-a)^2} (\varepsilon f'(mb) - (2-\varepsilon)f'(a)) + \frac{2}{(mb-a)^3} \int_0^1 (6t-2-\varepsilon) f(ta + m(1-t)b) dt \\ &= \frac{-1}{(mb-a)^2} (\varepsilon f'(mb) - (2-\varepsilon)f'(a)) + \frac{2}{(mb-a)^3} (6t-2-\varepsilon) f(ta + m(1-t)b) dt \Big|_0^1 \\ & - \frac{2}{(mb-a)^3} \int_0^1 (6t-2-\varepsilon) f(ta + m(1-t)b) \\ &= \frac{-1}{(mb-a)^2} (\varepsilon f'(mb) - (2-\varepsilon)f'(a)) + \frac{2}{(mb-a)^3} (4-\varepsilon)f(a) + (\varepsilon+2)f(mb) \\ & - \frac{12}{(mb-a)^3} \int_0^1 f(ta + m(1-t)b) \\ &= \frac{-1}{(mb-a)^2} (\varepsilon f'(mb) - (2-\varepsilon)f'(a)) + \frac{2}{(mb-a)^3} (4-\varepsilon)f(a) + (\varepsilon+2)f(mb) \\ & - \frac{12}{(mb-a)^4} \int_a^{mb} f(x) dx. \tag{1} \end{aligned}$$

Multiplying equality (1) with $\frac{(mb-a)^3}{12}$ and subtracting

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{2(1-\alpha)}{\beta(\alpha)} f(k) \text{ on both sides, we get} \\ & I \frac{(mb-a)^3}{12} - \frac{2(1-\alpha)}{\beta(\alpha)} f(k) \\ &= \frac{-(mb-a)}{12} (\varepsilon f'(mb) - (2-\varepsilon)f'(a)) + \frac{(4-\varepsilon)f(a) + (\varepsilon+2)f(mb)}{6} \\ & - \frac{1}{(mb-a)} \int_a^{mb} f(x) dx - \frac{2(1-\alpha)}{\beta(\alpha)} f(k) \\ &= \frac{-(mb-a)}{12} (\varepsilon f'(mb) - (2-\varepsilon)f'(a)) + \frac{(4-\varepsilon)f(a) + (\varepsilon+2)f(mb)}{6} \\ & - \frac{\beta(\alpha)}{\alpha(mb-a)} \left[\frac{\alpha}{\beta(\alpha)} \int_a^k f(x) dx - \frac{(1-\alpha)}{\beta(\alpha)} f(k) + \frac{\alpha}{\beta(\alpha)} \int_k^{mb} f(x) dx - \frac{(1-\alpha)}{\beta(\alpha)} f(k) \right] \\ &= \frac{-(mb-a)}{12} (\varepsilon f'(mb) - (2-\varepsilon)f'(a)) + \frac{(4-\varepsilon)f(a) + (\varepsilon+2)f(mb)}{6} \\ & - \frac{\beta(\alpha)}{\alpha(mb-a)} \left[({}^{CF}I_a^\alpha f)(k) + ({}^{CF}I_{mb}^\alpha f)(k) \right] \end{aligned}$$

Thus, we have

$$\left(\frac{(4-\varepsilon)f(a) + (\varepsilon+2)f(mb)}{2} \right) - \frac{\beta(\alpha)}{\alpha(mb-a)} \left[({}^{CF}I_a^\alpha f)(k) + ({}^{CF}I_{mb}^\alpha f)(k) \right]$$

$$-\frac{b-a}{12}(\varepsilon f'(mb) - (2-\varepsilon)f'(a)) + \frac{2(1-\alpha)}{\beta(\alpha)} f(k)$$

$$= \frac{(mb-a)^3}{12} \int_0^1 t(1-t)(2t-\varepsilon) f'''(ta+(1-t)b) dt.$$

This completes the proof.

3 Hermite-Hadamard Type Inequalities For Quasi-convex Functions

In this section, we obtained the parameterized error bounds for the Hermite-Hadamard type inequalities via a quasi-convex function.

Theorem 2 Under the assumption of Lemma 1. If $|f'''|^q$ is quasi-convex on $[a, b]$ and $q \geq 1$, then the following fractional parameterized inequality holds:

$$\left| \left(\frac{(4-\varepsilon)f(a) + (\varepsilon+2)f(mb)}{2} \right) - \frac{\beta(\alpha)}{\alpha(mb-a)} \left[({}^{CF}I_a^\alpha f)(k) + ({}^{CF}I_{mb}^\alpha f)(k) \right] - \frac{b-a}{12}(\varepsilon f'(mb) - (2-\varepsilon)f'(a)) + \frac{2(1-\alpha)}{\beta(\alpha)} f(k) \right|$$

$$\leq \frac{(mb-a)^3}{12} \begin{cases} \left(\frac{\varepsilon-1}{6} \right) \left[\max \left\{ |f'''(a)|^q, |f'''(b)|^q \right\} \right]^{\frac{1}{q}} & \varepsilon \geq 2, \\ \left(\frac{4\varepsilon^3 - \varepsilon^4}{48} + \frac{1-\varepsilon}{6} \right) \left[\max \left\{ |f'''(a)|^q, |f'''(b)|^q \right\} \right]^{\frac{1}{q}} & 0 < \varepsilon < 2, \\ \left(\frac{1-\varepsilon}{6} \right) \left[\max \left\{ |f'''(a)|^q, |f'''(b)|^q \right\} \right]^{\frac{1}{q}} & \varepsilon \leq 0, \end{cases}$$

where

$$\int_0^1 t(1-t)(2t-\varepsilon) dt = \begin{cases} \frac{\varepsilon-1}{6} & \varepsilon \geq 2, \\ \frac{4\varepsilon^3 - \varepsilon^4}{48} + \frac{1-\varepsilon}{6} & 0 < \varepsilon < 2, \\ \left(\frac{1-\varepsilon}{6} \right) & \varepsilon \leq 0. \end{cases}$$

Proof. By using the Lemma 1, since Hölder inequality of $|f'''|^q$, it follows that

$$\left| \left(\frac{(4-\varepsilon)f(a) + (\varepsilon+2)f(mb)}{2} \right) - \frac{\beta(\alpha)}{\alpha(mb-a)} \left[({}^{CF}I_a^\alpha f)(k) + ({}^{CF}I_{mb}^\alpha f)(k) \right] \right|$$

$$-\frac{b-a}{12}(\varepsilon f'(mb) - (2-\varepsilon)f'(a)) + \frac{2(1-\alpha)}{\beta(\alpha)} f(k)$$

$$\leq \frac{(mb-a)^3}{12} \int_0^1 t(1-t)(2t-\varepsilon) f'''(ta+(1-t)b) dt$$

$$\leq \frac{(mb-a)^3}{12} \left(\int_0^1 t(1-t)(2t-\varepsilon) dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \left(\int_0^1 t(1-t)(2t-\varepsilon) |f'''(ta+(1-t)b)|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}}.$$

By using the quasi-convexity of $|f'''|^q$, we get

$$\left| \left(\frac{(4-\varepsilon)f(a) + (\varepsilon+2)f(mb)}{2} \right) - \frac{\beta(\alpha)}{\alpha(mb-a)} \left[({}^{CF}I_a^\alpha f)(k) + ({}^{CF}I_{mb}^\alpha f)(k) \right] - \frac{b-a}{12}(\varepsilon f'(mb) - (2-\varepsilon)f'(a)) + \frac{2(1-\alpha)}{\beta(\alpha)} f(k) \right|$$

$$\leq \frac{(mb-a)^3}{12} \left(\int_0^1 t(1-t)(2t-\varepsilon) dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \left(\int_0^1 t(1-t)(2t-\varepsilon) |f'''(ta+(1-t)b)|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}}$$

$$\leq \frac{(mb-a)^3}{12} \left(\int_0^1 t(1-t)(2t-\varepsilon) dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \left(\int_0^1 t(1-t)(2t-\varepsilon) \max \left\{ |f'''(a)|^q, |f'''(b)|^q \right\} dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}}$$

$$\leq \frac{(mb-a)^3}{12} \left(\int_0^1 t(1-t)(2t-\varepsilon) dt \right) \left[\max \left\{ |f'''(a)|^q, |f'''(b)|^q \right\} \right]^{\frac{1}{q}}.$$

This completes the proof.

Remark 1 If we substitution $a \rightarrow b$, $b \rightarrow a$ and $\varepsilon \rightarrow 2-\varepsilon$ in Theorem 2, we have the futher generalization of Theorem 2.

Theorem 3 Under the assumption of Lemma 1. If $|f'''|^q$ is quasi-convex on $[a, b]$, $a \neq b$ and $q \geq 1$, then the following fractional parameterized inequality holds:

$$\left| \left(\frac{(4-\varepsilon)f(a) + (\varepsilon+2)f(mb)}{2} \right) - \frac{\beta(\alpha)}{\alpha(mb-a)} \left[({}^{CF}I_a^\alpha f)(k) + ({}^{CF}I_{mb}^\alpha f)(k) \right] - \frac{b-a}{12}(\varepsilon f'(mb) - (2-\varepsilon)f'(a)) + \frac{2(1-\alpha)}{\beta(\alpha)} f(k) \right|$$

$$\leq \begin{cases} \frac{|mb-a|^3}{12} \left(\frac{\varepsilon-1}{6} \right) \left[\max \left\{ |f'''(a)|^q, |f'''(b)|^q \right\} \right]^{\frac{1}{q}} & \varepsilon \geq 2, \\ \frac{|mb-a|^3}{12} \left(\frac{4\varepsilon^3 - \varepsilon^4}{48} + \frac{1-\varepsilon}{6} \right) \left[\max \left\{ |f'''(a)|^q, |f'''(b)|^q \right\} \right]^{\frac{1}{q}} & 0 < \varepsilon < 2, \\ \frac{|mb-a|^3}{12} \left(\frac{1-\varepsilon}{6} \right) \left[\max \left\{ |f'''(a)|^q, |f'''(b)|^q \right\} \right]^{\frac{1}{q}} & \varepsilon \leq 0. \end{cases}$$

Corollary 1 If we choose $\varepsilon = 1$ in Theorem 2, then we obtain the following inequality

$$\left| \frac{f(a)+f(b)}{2} - \frac{b-a}{12} (f'(mb)-f'(a)) - \frac{\beta(\alpha)}{\alpha(mb-a)} \left[({}^{CF}I_a^\alpha f)(k) + ({}^{CF}I_{mb}^\alpha f)(k) \right] + \frac{2(1-\alpha)}{\beta(\alpha)} f(k) \right| \leq \frac{(mb-a)^3}{192} \left[\max \left\{ |f'''(a)|^q, |f'''(b)|^q \right\}^{\frac{1}{q}} \right].$$

Additionally if we using different parameterized values in Theorem 2, then we have the following Corollaries.

Corollary 2 If we put $\mathcal{E} = 0$ in Theorem 2, then we get

$$\left| \frac{2f(a)+f(b)}{3} + \frac{b-a}{6} f'(a) - \frac{\beta(\alpha)}{\alpha(mb-a)} \left[({}^{CF}I_a^\alpha f)(k) + ({}^{CF}I_{mb}^\alpha f)(k) \right] + \frac{2(1-\alpha)}{\beta(\alpha)} f(k) \right| \leq \frac{(mb-a)^3}{72} \left[\max \left\{ |f'''(a)|^q, |f'''(b)|^q \right\}^{\frac{1}{q}} \right].$$

Corollary 3 If we put $\mathcal{E} = 0.5$ in Theorem 2, then we get

$$\left| \frac{7f(a)+5f(b)}{12} - \frac{b-a}{24} (f'(mb)-3f'(a)) - \frac{\beta(\alpha)}{\alpha(mb-a)} \left[({}^{CF}I_a^\alpha f)(k) + ({}^{CF}I_{mb}^\alpha f)(k) \right] + \frac{2(1-\alpha)}{\beta(\alpha)} f(k) \right| \leq \frac{71(mb-a)^3}{9216} \left[\max \left\{ |f'''(a)|^q, |f'''(b)|^q \right\}^{\frac{1}{q}} \right].$$

Corollary 4 If we put $\mathcal{E} = 3$ in Theorem 2, then we get

$$\left| \frac{f(a)+5f(b)}{6} - \frac{b-a}{12} (3f'(mb)-f'(a)) - \frac{\beta(\alpha)}{\alpha(mb-a)} \left[({}^{CF}I_a^\alpha f)(k) + ({}^{CF}I_{mb}^\alpha f)(k) \right] + \frac{2(1-\alpha)}{\beta(\alpha)} f(k) \right| \leq \frac{(mb-a)^3}{36} \left[\max \left\{ |f'''(a)|^q, |f'''(b)|^q \right\}^{\frac{1}{q}} \right].$$

Corollary 5 If we put $\mathcal{E} = -2$ in Theorem 2, then we get

$$\left| f(a) + \frac{b-a}{6} (f'(mb)+2f'(a)) - \frac{\beta(\alpha)}{\alpha(mb-a)} \left[({}^{CF}I_a^\alpha f)(k) + ({}^{CF}I_{mb}^\alpha f)(k) \right] + \frac{2(1-\alpha)}{\beta(\alpha)} f(k) \right| \leq \frac{(mb-a)^3}{24} \left[\max \left\{ |f'''(a)|^q, |f'''(b)|^q \right\}^{\frac{1}{q}} \right].$$

Corollary 6 If we put $\mathcal{E} = -3$ in Theorem 2, then we get

$$\left| \frac{7f(a)-f(b)}{6} + \frac{b-a}{12} (3f'(mb)+5f'(a)) - \frac{\beta(\alpha)}{\alpha(mb-a)} \left[({}^{CF}I_a^\alpha f)(k) + ({}^{CF}I_{mb}^\alpha f)(k) \right] + \frac{2(1-\alpha)}{\beta(\alpha)} f(k) \right| \leq \frac{(mb-a)^3}{18} \left[\max \left\{ |f'''(a)|^q, |f'''(b)|^q \right\}^{\frac{1}{q}} \right].$$

Corollary 7 If we put $\mathcal{E} = -5$ in Theorem 2, then we get

$$\left| \frac{3f(a)-f(b)}{2} + \frac{b-a}{12} (5f'(mb)+7f'(a)) - \frac{\beta(\alpha)}{\alpha(mb-a)} \left[({}^{CF}I_a^\alpha f)(k) + ({}^{CF}I_{mb}^\alpha f)(k) \right] + \frac{2(1-\alpha)}{\beta(\alpha)} f(k) \right|$$

3.1 Special Means

We shall consider the following special means.

(a) The Arithmetic mean:

$$A = A(a,b) := \frac{a+b}{2}, \quad a, b \geq 0.$$

(b) The Geometric Mean:

$$G = G(a,b) := \sqrt{ab}, \quad a, b \geq 0.$$

(c) The Logarithmic Mean:

$$L(a,b) := \frac{b-a}{\ln b - \ln a}, \quad a, b > 0, a \neq b.$$

(d) The Generalized Logarithmic Mean:

$$L_r^r = L_r^r(a,b) := \left[\frac{b-a}{(r+1)(b-a)} \right]^{\frac{1}{r}}.$$

Proposition 1 For $a, b \in \mathbb{R}$, $n \in \mathbb{N}$, $n \geq 3$, and $\varepsilon \neq 1$, then we have

$$\left| A(a^n, b^n; 4 - \varepsilon, 2 + \varepsilon) - \frac{n(b-a)(\varepsilon-1)}{6} A(a^{n-1}, b^{n-1}; \varepsilon-2, \varepsilon) - L_n^n(a, b) \right|$$

$$\begin{cases} \frac{|b-a|^3(\varepsilon-1)n(n-1)(n-2)}{72} \left[\max\{|a|^{n-3}, |f'''(b)|^{n-3}\} \right] & \varepsilon \geq 2, \\ \frac{|b-a|^3(\varepsilon-1)n(n-1)(n-2)}{12} \left(\frac{4\varepsilon^3 - \varepsilon^4}{48} + \frac{1-\varepsilon}{6} \right) \left[\max\{|f'''(a)|^{n-3}, |f'''(b)|^{n-3}\} \right] & 0 < \varepsilon < 2, \\ \frac{|b-a|^3(\varepsilon-1)n(n-1)(n-2)}{72} \left[\max\{|f'''(a)|^{n-3}, |f'''(b)|^{n-3}\} \right] & \varepsilon \leq 0. \end{cases}$$

Proof. The assertion follows from Theorem 3, employing the $f(x) = x^n$, $\alpha = q = m = 1$ and $\beta(0) = \beta(1) = 1$.

Proposition 2 For $a, b \in \mathbb{R}$, $n \in \mathbb{N}$, $n \geq 3$, and $\varepsilon \neq 1$, then we have

$$\left| A(a^n, b^n) - \frac{(b-a)^2 n(n-1)}{12} L_{n-2}^{n-2}(a, b) - L_n^n(a, b) \right|$$

$$\leq \frac{(b-a)^3 n(n-1)(n-2)}{192} \left[\max\{|a|^{n-3}, |f'''(b)|^{n-3}\} \right].$$

Proof. The assertion follows from Corollary 1, employing the $f(x) = x^n$, $\alpha = m = q = 1$ and $\beta(0) = \beta(1) = 1$.

4 Conclusion

Mainly, the paper endeavors to make significant contributions to the theoretical foundations of fractional calculus, deepen insights into convex functions within the fractional calculus framework, and stimulate ongoing research efforts in the field of fractional H-H inequalities.

The paper introduces a novel fractional parameterized inequality of the Hermite-Hadamard type (H-H). This equality is established for the m -Caputao-Fabrizio fractional operator, and functions with third derivative in absolute values are quasi-convex, with the main results presented in Theorem 2, and Theorem 3. Additionally, it demonstrates that by assigning specific values to the parameter in the parameterized inequality, several new results for Hermite-Hadamard-type (H-H) inequalities are obtained. Furthermore, it highlights that these special cases encompass previously known results, as illustrated in Corollaries 1, and 2-7. The obtained results are applied to establish two new inequalities concerning special means of real numbers. These applications utilize the parameterized Hermite-Hadamard-type (H-H) inequality and are detailed in Propositions 1, and 2.

Declaration of Ethical Standards

Not applicable.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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